

Strengthening Character Education Management of Students Based on SARUMA Culture in Learning Pancasila and Citizenship Education in High Schools, South Halmahera Regency

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Abstract:- The influence of globalization has resulted in today's young generation being more proud of foreign cultures than our own. Our culture has a very big role in developing the character of young people in Indonesia, especially the "SARUMA" culture. In developing the "SARUMA" culture in South Halmahera District High School to capture foreign culture, the attention of local and state governments. Therefore, the central and regional governments must work hard to increase the strengthening of character education at the central, provincial, and district/city levels. The character education in the era of globalization plays an active role in overcoming the moral crisis that hit South Halmahera Regency, North Maluku Province. Strengthening character education has a very important role such as finding solutions or solving problems, making decisions by consensus, and being able to reduce conflicts that often occur both at school and in the community.

The aims of this research are; 1), to describe and explain the values of character education for students based on the "SARUMA" culture in senior high schools in South Halmahera Regency, 2) to describe and explain the form of strengthening the character education of students based on the "SARUMA" culture in high schools in South Halmahera Regency.

The research used descriptive qualitative method. Data collected at the beginning of the study through observation, interviews, and direct documentation was recorded for analysis. The data were analyzed using the developed model. There are three components of the model used in analyzing qualitative data, namely; 1) the data reduction (data reduction), 2), data Presentation (data display), 3), drawing Conclusions/Verification. In the final flow of this data analysis is drawing conclusions and verification. The results of this study are strengthening the character education of students based on the "SARUMA" culture which was developed at the High School of South Halmahera Regency.

Keywords:- SARUMA culture, strengthening character education, high school.

I. INTRODUCTION

Strengthening character education is a vital need that is very urgent and a concern for various parties. This shows that something is lacking in education today. Everyone agrees that strengthening character education is very important in the world of education (Tu, et al., 1996, p. 13). The more incessant friction and encouragement from the community for the importance of character education shows dissatisfaction with the quality of education. Character education is considered as one way out of the current educational deficit (Koesoema, 2015). The decline in moral quality in human life in Indonesia today, especially among students, demands character education (Jacobus & Hendriana, 2016).

There are several things that need to be treated at the planning stage of character education, such as: 1) identifying the types of activities in schools that can be realized in character education that must be mastered, and realized by students in everyday life. For this reason, the implementation of strengthening character education is realized in three groups of activities, namely integrated in thematic learning, integrated with school management, and integrated through extra-curricular activities, 2) developed learning materials with various types of activities in schools, 3) developed implementation design for activities in schools (objectives, materials, schedules, teachers, evaluations, and facilities), and 4) prepared supporting facilities for the implementation of character building programs in schools (Zulhijrah, 2015). In planning character education programs in schools, it refers to the types of school activities to develop goals, activity targets, substance of activities, implementation, organization, time, place, and other supporting facilities.

The family and community environment is strived to carry out a process of strengthening character education from parents and community leaders towards very noble moral behavior developed in schools so that it becomes a daily activity at home and in their respective communities. This needs to be done through school committees, and foundations as well as parent meetings, visits or parent activities related to activities and families with the aim of equalizing opinions in order to build the character of students at school, at home, and in the community, especially the community in South Halmahera Regency.

Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education, mention that: Article 1. In this Presidential Regulation what is meant by: Strengthening Character Education, hereinafter abbreviated as PPK, is an educational movement under the responsibility of the education unit to strengthen the character of students through harmonization of the heart, if taste, thought, and sport with the involvement and cooperation between educational units, families, and communities as part of the National Movement, Mental Revolution, GNRM). Thus character education can also be strengthened with the "SARUMA" culture in order to increase awareness among the community, especially the people in South Halmahera Regency, North Maluku Province. Foreign culture that comes in South Halmahera Regency is growing rapidly and has a broad impact on the social environment. Culture can be described as an accumulation of knowledge, practices and beliefs about the relationship of living things to one another that develops by adaptive and hereditary processes by human culture, especially the "SARUMA" culture (Sahib, et al., 2019). The decline in moral quality in Indonesian human life today, especially among high school students, demands character education (Jacobus&Hendriana, 2016).

In this case, the strengthening of character education in high school is not optimal because the environmental conditions are not supportive. The contributions that have been made by parents and the community in the education process for the nation's children have not been maximized. Since many families and communities today cannot be relied upon as a basis for strengthening character education for the society. The current situation and conditions is a big challenge for the government, educational institutions including teachers, to further improve the character education of students in schools (Fullan, 2001). Schools are required to instill good values and help students strengthen the character education of high school students with better "SARUMA" cultural values in South Halmahera Regency.

In the implementation of strengthening character education in schools, all components need to be involved, including existing components in the education system, such as curriculum, infrastructure, financing, and human resources. In the implementation of strengthening character education in schools to be optimal, effective, and efficient, effective and efficient management activities are needed (Mulyasa, 2016). School culture-based character education is an activity to create a better school climate and environment to support the strengthening of character education in order to overcome the atmosphere of classrooms and must involve all systems, structures, and education actors in schools (Rahman, et al., 2019). In the implementation of strengthening school culture-based character education, it includes school governance, curriculum, and school rules and regulations.

Strengthening school culture-based character education is focused on habituation and the formation of a "SARUMA" culture which represents the main values, namely strengthening student character education in high school, South Halmahera Regency. This habit is integrated

into high school activities which are reflected in a conducive school environment. Problems that threaten the integrity and future of the nation, Indonesia also faces challenges and competition on the global stage, such as the low human development index, threatening the nation's competitiveness, the physical weakness of Indonesian children due to lack of reliable skills, low sense of art, aesthetics and creativity ethical knowledge that has not been formed during the education period (Effendy, 2017). The "SARUMA" culture has a very important role in the character development of adolescent children. School-age teenagers tend to follow all that is trending without thinking about the impact it will have in the future. Thus, there are many activities that become deviations that can be carried out by teenagers. In addition, the "SARUMA" culture is interpreted as a system with the first reason being that the government's decision to implement regional autonomy is one of the steps to raise regional potential. This can be seen in the news in print and electronic media that highlight the "SARUMA" culture in South Halmahera Regency to be able to develop the preservation of the "SARUMA" culture such as: Bari culture and Fautuh. Both Bacan are South Halmahera Regency which has a lot of "SARUMA" culture to attract foreign cultural influences. Third, in the subjects in high school, there is local content material which is the basis for introducing the "SARUMA" culture of foreign tribes to students in South Halmahera Regency.

In the implementation of character education, it has a very strategic role to implement the preservation of the "SARUMA" culture. In relation to the role in forming the character of high school students, it would be better if it was integrated with the "SARUMA" culture. The "SARUMA" culture for the Bacan community is in the form of nature conservation, culture, customs, tourism potential and the creative economy. South Halmahera Regency, which is a wide district and has a variety of individual characteristics that underlie the development of its community character. This is in accordance with the definition of character in the Big Indonesian Dictionary, namely, psychological traits, character, character, morals or character that distinguishes one person from another. So it is necessary to strengthen character education integrated with the "SARUMA" culture of the Bacan tribe, South Halmahera Regency.

Education is a process of transmitting culture to improve human quality (Knowles, 1974, p. 116). In the process of improving human quality, there needs to be optimal utilization of resources, so the application of management principles in education is very important. Quality education that will produce quality human resources and quality education must be held with quality management (Suyitno, et al., 2014, p. 60). Based on the previous assumptions, the effort to support the success of the process of strengthening character education in South Halmahera High Schools is carried out with a better management system. The implementation of management must always be carried out systematically and consistently through steps called management functions (Salim, 2015).

The management functions used in the preparation of character education strengthening programs are carried out through the stages of planning, implementation, supervision, and evaluation results. This is the basis for preparing the program for the following year. In the context of strengthening character education, each school has a very noble school vision and mission. In this very noble mission, it has many rich values that become clusters and will help realize the relationship of the noble mission (Koesoma, 2015).

Character education is one of the school programs compiled, namely: SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency by strengthening character education based on the "SARUMA" culture that animates the entire educational process in schools. This "SARUMA" culture is the basic foundation that animates the vision and mission of the three schools. By compiling a program for strengthening character education, it can be carried out at the planning, implementation, and monitoring stages. Based on this description, this research answers several questions as follows: (1). The values of character education for students based on the "SARUMA" culture developed in senior high schools in South Halmahera Regency. (2). The form of strengthening the character education of students based on the "SARUMA" culture developed in senior high schools, South Halmahera Regency.

II. LITERARY REVIEW

Sagita (2021) conducted a research about Management of Culture-Based Student Character Education Strengthening entitled *Manajemen Pendidikan Karakter Siswa Berbasis Budaya Sekolah Studi Kasus Di Smk Dwi Bhakti Ciledug Kabupaten Cirebon*. The research on the management of student character education based on school culture is the focus of research that has not been widely studied because the character of students in school culture has not been systematically and planned integrated. This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study research design and purposive sampling and snowball sampling data sources include Principal, Deputy Head of Curriculum, Deputy Head of Student Affairs, Subject Teacher, Extracurricular Supervisor. The research instrument is a researcher with data collection based on the method, namely in depth interviews, observation and documentation studies and data triangulation. While the data analysis was carried out by collecting, reduction, and consensus, the validity of the data was carried out including credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability tests.

Panoyo, et al., (2019) also wrote a research about Management of Character Education Strengthening entitled *ManajemenPenguatanPendidikanKarakterPadaSekolahMenengahAtas*. This study aims to describe and analyze the data on the management of character education in the regency of Sidoarjo with case studies in SMAN 1 Krian and SMAN 1 Taman. The management component begins with the planning, organization, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of character education strengthening at SMAN 1 Krian and SMAN 1 Taman Sidoarjo. Management of related

search results Strengthening character education in Sidoarjo regency (several case studies in SMAN 1 Krian and SMAN 1 Taman) shows that planning for strengthening character education should pay attention to at least five aspects, namely refer to the school's vision and mission, conduct assessments to identify the school's potential, formulate and determine values. Core character values to be developed, school curricula are prepared with all components of the school and teachers implement character-based learning tools (RPP).

As for further research which also discusses character education, namely Fardani, et al., (2022) entitled *ManajemenStrategidalamPenyelenggaraanPenguatanPendidikanKarakter(PPPK)*. The purpose of this study is to describe and explain the processes of planning, implementation and control of the strategy for implementing the strengthening of character education in MAN 1 Klaten. This study uses qualitative research methods and the data is analyzed with data reduction, data presentation and also drawing conclusions and verification. The results of this study provide three research conclusions, including strategic planning that includes: (1) based on national character, religious values and also culture, and (2) systematic. Second, the implementation of this strategy includes: (1) use of the madrasa environment, (2) habituation programs for the activities contained in the madrasa environment, (3) the establishing and maintaining cooperative relationships with other parties, (4) setting an example for the environment of the madrasa, (5) developing the culture of the madrasa, (6) organizing programs of learning services, (7) strengthen madrasa rules and (8) strengthen character education through co-curricular and extracurricular programs in a sustainable manner and systematically. Third, monitoring the character education implementation strategy includes: (1) monitoring by all teachers through several stages, (2) conducting evidence-based analysis of results, and (3) monitoring and continuous improvement.

Several previous studies discussed strengthening character education and the importance of it to be done, but what is different from this research is that this research focuses on strengthening culture-based character education specifically on Saruma culture in Pancasila and Citizenship Education Learning in High Schools, South Halmahera Regency.

III. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Strategic Management

Management Strategy is defined by a series of managerial actions and managerial decisions that seek to determine or determine organizational performance for a long period of time (Hunger & Wheelen, 2003, p. 4). Meanwhile, Nawawi (2000, p. 148–149) explains that this strategic management has four meanings. One of them, this strategic management is defined as a series of processes and activities of making a comprehensive and fundamental decision, which is followed by the determination of a way of implementing it, which is designed and designed by top management, and then implemented by all levels within the organization, which is intended to can meet or achieve

certain planned goals (Sukmawaty, et al., 2022). The existence of good education management is a determinant of whether or not an educational unit is good (Amalia&Zuhro, 2022,p. 2372; Andini, et al., 2022).

B. Character

Simaremare (2013) stated that the character comes from the Greek which means to mark and focus on how to apply good values in real actions or everyday behavior. Therefore it's the behavior of people who are dishonest, cruel, cheating, and greedy is said to be a person of bad character, while well-behaved, honest, and helpful person is said to be a person who has good character or glorious.

C. Education

According to Raharjo (2010) a complete and comprehensive education does not only shape young people into intelligent and good individuals, but also shapes them to become good actors for changes in their own lives, which in turn will contribute to changes in the social order to become more just, kind, and humane. Character education can be interpreted as education that provides values, character, character, morals, or education that shape character someone with the aim of developing abilities students to become better and implement it in everyday life wholeheartedly, because the good or bad of a country depends on the character his people Buchory (2015).

D. Culture

Liliweri (2014:276) explains culture as a deposit knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, meanings, hierarchies, religions, records of time, roles, certain relations, universe concepts, material objects, and thoughts recognized by a group of people who are then passed down from one generation to another. Futheremore, Rahman & Letlora, (2018) states that Culture will show the rules of the game that apply in a group or organization. Organizational culture allows for changes due to adjustments to the situation to the applicable rules of the game. The rules of the game are formed differently which then if it is deemed suitable to be carried out, it will be passed on to the next generation (Rahman, 2019; Sukmawaty, et al., 2022).

E. Objective of the Study

The objectives of this study are 1) to describe and explain the values of character education for students based on the "SARUMA" culture in senior high schools in South Halmahera Regency and 2) to describe and explain the form of strengthening the character education of students based on the "SARUMA" culture in high schools in Halmahera South Regency.

F. Method

The research used descriptive qualitative method to answer problems based on the following considerations: 1) naturalistic qualitative research, which presents a holistic form (comprehensive) in analyzing a phenomenon, 2) this study is more sensitive to capture descriptive qualitative information, by maintaining the integrity of the subject under study (Bakri, 2013). The data that has been collected in this study were then analyzed using a qualitative descriptive approach. Data collected on the beginning of the research through observation, interviews, and direct

documentation was recorded for analysis.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. The Values of Character Education of Students Based on the "SARUMA" Culture Developed in High Schools in South Halmahera Regency

The values of strengthening student character education based on the "SARUMA" culture are religious, honest, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, the spirit of nationalism or nationalism. Love the homeland, appreciate achievements, communicative, love peace, love to read, care for the environment, care about social, and responsibility. Strengthening character education requires careful learning planning for students at SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency. "SARUMA" Cultural-Based Character Education Strengthening Planning is the process of determining organizational goals and selecting students' future actions to achieve goals effectively and efficiently (Sonhadji, 2014). Good planning must actually be based on the results of the evaluation that has been carried out (Salim, 2015). This is in line with the preparation of character education strengthening programs carried out by SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, SMK Misbahul Aulad, South Halmahera Regency, which is always preceded by an evaluation of the previous annual program. This will form the basis for the preparation of the program for the following year. In the context of strengthening character education, each educational institution has a very noble school vision and mission. This very noble mission has many rich values that become clusters that will help realize the relationship of the noble mission.

Character education is one of the school programs organized at SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency as a reinforcement of student character education based on the "SARUMA" culture that animates all educational learning in high school. This "SARUMA" culture is the basic foundation that animates the vision and mission of these three schools. Vision describes the future reach to be achieved, and its elements of a value system, mission, goals, and expectations for the future role of the nation and state, especially high school in South Halmahera Regency. The formulation of a good vision can contain values that are fought for to achieve a better future reach (Hidayah, et al., 2014). In accordance with Koesoema's opinion (2015) that the vision and mission of educational institutions is expressed in core values that are very special and different from other institutions and must be fought for (Koesoema, 2015).

Vision of SMA Negeri 7 South Halmahera Regency: Develop and compete to make SMA 7 South Halmahera Regency into an independent and superior school in the fields of science and technology and IMTAK.

School Mission: (1) Improving discipline and responsibility in teaching and learning activities. (2) Teachers and students are encouraged to achieve

achievements according to their talents and interests. (3) Increase faith and piety through religious development and character. (4) Implement participatory management and involve all school members.

The vision of SMA Alkhairaat, South Halmahera Regency: to realize SMA Alkhairaat Labuha as a school whose students are intellectually, emotionally, and spiritually intelligent, as well as physically healthy in the era of globalization.

The School's Mission: (1) to increase the experience of faith and piety in every school community towards the religious teachings adopted to serve as a way of life, (2) to excel in implementing the curriculum at the education unit level, (3) optimizing the learning process, guidance and assessment effectively and efficiently (4) organizing an educational process that is oriented to the quality of education and based on intellectual, emotional and spiritual attitudes in each subject, (5) improving the positive performance of science and information technology and Islamic modern culture, (6) enforce certain days for foreign languages and (7) creating healthy and superior students who are able to compete at local, national and international levels.

Vision of SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency: to produce graduates who are independent, honest and devout and have knowledge according to the needs of the world/industrial business and able to compete with the era of globalization.

a) Vocational School Mission

Prepare business and management group students to become productive, skilled, honest and pious middle-level workers based on their chosen study program through teaching and learning activities in schools and the business world/industrial world in a programmatic manner by utilizing available facilities and resources in order to fill employment opportunities and independent and able to adapt to advances in science and technology in the context of filling national development.

The vision and mission of the three institutions are clearly seen to have very noble values in schools that are different from other schools in general. These values are very different from one institution to another because of different traditional roots. The vision and mission of private schools, especially Alkhairaat High School, and MisbahulAulad Vocational School, South Halmahera Regency have a "SARUMA" culture which is the basis for strengthening character education in schools. Meanwhile, the vision and mission of public schools come from the same source, which is contained in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution and translated into educational objectives as stated in the applicable National Education System Law (Koesoema, 20015). The noble values of the "SARUMA" culture which are sourced from the vision and mission of the school, SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK Misbahul Aulad, South Halmahera Regency are

Religious, Togetherness (mutual help), harmony, love of peace, responsibility, discipline, and transparent.

Religion is reflecting faith in God which is manifested through the behavior of carrying out the teachings of the religion adopted, respecting religious differences, upholding a tolerant attitude towards other religions and beliefs, and living in harmony and peace with adherents of other religions. *Gotongroyong* means respecting the spirit of cooperation and working together to solve common problems; happy to socialize and make friends with other people; and provide assistance to those who are poor, marginalized, and in need of assistance.

Harmony is a mutual respect and maintaining order in society, nation and state. In order for harmony to occur, it is better to maintain good behavior in social life. Peace-loving is the behavior that underlies the attitudes, words, and actions that make others feel happy and secure in their presence. Life becomes peaceful with the presence of peace-loving individuals. Peace-loving is the basis of behavior: caring for others; helpful; responsible; forgiving; promote peace in interactions with others, likes to help. Responsibility is human awareness of intentional or unintentional behavior or actions. Such as: carrying out tasks to completion, completing tasks on time, admitting mistakes when doing, carrying out tasks that are their obligations, making reports after completing activities.

Discipline is the attitude of obeying rules and regulations. Discipline requires integrity to bring about the desired state. Discipline starts from small things, such as dividing time for study and play, so that both are done in a balanced way. Examples of disciplinary behavior in the school environment; obey school rules, arrive on time, don't talk when the teacher explains, throw trash in its place. Transparent is an attitude of openness between fellow human beings, both individuals and groups.

Observing the source of values from the vision and mission of SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency, it is clear that the wealth of values desired together, including the desire to embody students in order to have a character based on a better "SARUMA" culture. A person is said to have good character where he loses has three habits, namely thinking about good things (habits of mind), wanting good things (habits of heart) and doing good things (habits of action).

In line with that, SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, South Halmahera Regency wants the same thing to give birth to students who have good character, it is necessary to develop a character education program in spiritual development activities, faith building, mental coaching, and discipline through school rules, coaching aesthetics,

and sportsmanship in extracurricular activities, habituation activities, exemplary, and teaching and learning activities in schools. Based on this vision, it is necessary to develop a program through various activities held in schools, namely through teaching and learning activities in schools, through the culture of the education unit, extracurricular activities, and through community participation.

In preparing the character education program, SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency, deem it necessary to have parties, namely foundations, school principals, educators and education staff, parents, associations and community leaders. Involvement of all school components for program planning is the first step taken by schools to succeed in character education. The main requirement for effective and sustainable character education is to involve the entire community, namely the principal, the teacher council, non-educational employees, from security officers, cleaners, and to the smallest environment, namely parents (Koesoema, 2015).

All programs that have been prepared will be more effective and efficient if they are supported by adequate infrastructure. Supporting facilities or facilities planned for SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency are cleaning equipment, trash boxes, honesty boxes, healthy canteens, and designing a conducive school environment, classrooms. The trash box provided by the school is a means to familiarize students with a healthy living culture at school. A clean living culture can work well if there is socialization about the meaning of healthy living and maintaining cleanliness with the availability of supporting facilities, namely trash cans that have been distinguished between organic and non-organic waste.

B. The Form of Strengthening Character Education of Students Based on the "SARUMA" Culture Developed in High Schools in South Halmahera Regency

The implementation of strengthening character education basically refers to the cultural value "SARUMA" which is used as a spirit and animates the entire educational process at SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency. The implementation of strengthening character education in these three schools is focused on the "SARUMA" cultural values which are integrated in religious development programs, togetherness (mutual cooperation), harmony, love of peace, responsibility, discipline, and transparency. The character education implementation program is implemented through several strategies and uses the following approaches: Integrating values and ethics in each subject, internalizing positive values instilled by all school members (principals, teachers and parents), habituation and training, giving examples and role models, creating an atmosphere of character in schools, and civilizing (Suryani, et al., 2015).

"SARUMA" cultural values developed in schools, both SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency with the aim of developing students' personalities who are intelligent and have character, as well as being a fortress of resilience for students in facing the phenomenon of the decline of adult character. This approach, directs students to the formation of a person who respects and loves oneself, others and God, becomes a mature, mature, independent, responsible person, becomes a person who can distinguish good, right and wrong actions, becomes a person who reflects an attitude of mutual love, compassion, compassion, self-sacrifice, friendship, care for the fate of others, the poor, and care for the environment to become a person who is disciplined, obedient and obedient to applicable rules and norms, and becomes a person who has mutual respect, please help, cooperation, forgive, forgive, be a neat person, clean, be simple, honest, skilled, in the arts and sports.

It was observed that Saruma's culture is so rich in noble values that we want and strive for together, including the desire to embody the spirit of Saruma's culture for the sake of divinity and grace, inspiring teachers to define the teaching profession. as a call to the soul for commitment, conscience and a sense of noble love. in education services, aware of the importance of youth education, aware of the importance of value education. Students as educated people are seen as embryos of life that are still in the process of growing that must be appreciated and touched with love, in order to grow and develop properly. The duties and responsibilities as teachers in schools are to educate, direct, and form students with the same cultural values that come from the heart, namely love, so that they grow and develop into mature individuals, both in terms of intellect and intelligence their personality. The teacher is present in the midst of the students as a person who cares, empathizes, and is loyal and ultimately brings and guides students to the true goals of education.

The task of education is to guide and direct the growth and development of students from stage to stage of life until they reach the point of optimal ability, with the function of providing facilities that can facilitate educational tasks to run smoothly. So that it was inspired by the cultural spirit of Saruma to move the principal and staff of the teacher council to think about work systems and strategies for empowering all available resources in schools to make the implementation of strengthening character education a success (Saminan, 2015). In the successful implementation of strengthening character education in schools, it is necessary to divide the roles of each party involved in strengthening character education. The principal's role is to carry out its function as a manager in all school activities by building good communication between teachers, education staff, and parents, actively assisting and motivating teacher performance in every activity and through teacher council meetings, urging and reminding all school members to provide services with the heart, being a good role model and role model, namely attitudes, words and actions, and given awards for teachers who excel in carrying out their service duties well.

The role of the principal provides clear direction on the implementation of character education, with regard to implementation instructions and technical work instructions that must be understood by teachers and other school members, namely in the form of both practical and guided guidance during its implementation. Leadership behavior, especially principals in strengthening character education, is modeled by subordinates with various risks, shows behavior that is consistent with high ethical and moral standards, is motivated by subordinates, by increasing subordinates' optimism to work on the basis of noble values, providing intellectual stimulus to students subordinates to solve problems logically, critically at school, and able to pay attention to the needs of subordinates, and meet the needs of students according to the expectations of parents and society.

The implementation of "SARUMA" cultural values planting, namely through spiritual development activities, can be described: Daily prayers are carried out individually or collectively, taken from the scriptures and church traditions. Collective prayer activities are carried out every day to start and end each learning activity at school, which is led by students and is carried out alternately. In carrying out prayers, the school makes a schedule to be carried out in each class, and the teacher appoints students to lead the prayer when the learning activities in the class begin, and the learning activities in the class have been completed. Thus all students can follow carefully.

Students are given alternate assignments, namely both Muslims and Christians, and always respect each other in carrying out prayers together at school. The angelus/queen of heaven prays at 12.00 noon led by students who are determined from each class and other school members are answered according to the order. In carrying out this prayer, all school members who are in the classroom, as well as outside the classroom, and are Christian or Muslim, can be temporarily suspended from ongoing activities, so that they can pray together according to their respective religions and beliefs. Celebrating the Christmas celebration is carried out by forming a committee, coordinating with parents, class associations, students from each class. The implementation of this activity is in early December. The school invites parents of students, both Christian and Muslim, to ask for blessings from parents so that they can take the exam with better results.

Activities during the holy month of Ramadan which were held at SMA Negeri 7, SMA Alkhairaat, and SMK MisbahulAulad, South Halmahera Regency, namely with each school forming a committee that was given responsibility for other Christian students to become committees based on the results of consensus deliberation. With activities in the holy month of Ramadan, the committee invites Islamic preachers to be able to provide material for 1 week as follows: (1) Pesantren Kilat, about religious lectures, (2) invite students to read the Qur'an well, (3) teach students reading prayers. / dhikr together, (4) teaching students to pray (5) teaching students to respect differences between religious communities, and 6) teaching students, namely mutual respect for fellow human beings

both at school, at home, and in the student community is located. Thus the motto of the Bacan community (SARUMA) of South Halmahera Regency, namely *LipuNiKaHidupanga Kita*. This means that South Halmahera Regency is the place where we live together, regardless of religion, ethnicity, and if all the people in the area of South Halmahera Regency are a big "SARUMA" family.

The implementation of strengthening "SARUMA" culture-based character education in spiritual activities, namely school is a typical activity that is carried out routinely and made into a tradition. In carrying out this activity, it is necessary to adjust the schedule for joint provisions. This is in line with the opinion of Salim, (2015) that routine activities must be carried out continuously, consistently, in accordance with the determination of the schedule. The implementation of character education strengthening activities through routine spiritual activities is also in line with the opinion of Koesoema, (2015) that an institution will have certain characters that have become common habits that can trust and carry out community regularly and sustainably.

V. CONCLUSION

Strengthening student character education based on the "SARUMA" culture is a value that animates the entire educational process in schools, which in this case is the "SARUMA" culture-based student character education developed at the High School of South Halmahera Regency including: religious values, honesty, tolerant, disciplined, hardworking, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, love for the homeland, respect for achievement, communicative, love peace, love to read, care for the environment, care about social, and be responsible. Thus, the character values of students based on the "SARUMA" culture include: character, Pancasila, literary appreciation, as well as exemplary historical figures, and national leaders (cultural conservation).

The form of strengthening student character education based on the "SARUMA" culture which was developed at the High School of South Halmahera Regency is an effort made by teachers and parents in educating students so that they have the desired characters, called: characters that are in accordance with moral values, nation and state and have ethics and culture, including the "SARUMA" culture in South Halmahera Regency.

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